

THE COMPARISON OF PSYCHOLOGICAL HEALTH AND JOB BURNOUT OF FEMALE ATHLETIC AND NON-ATHLETIC TEACHERS OF MIANDOAB TOWN, IRAN IN 2016-2017

Mostafa Mostafa pourⁱ, Vadoud Shoshtary,

Mortaza Khodayi, Auoub Izadi,

Yousef Esmayilian, Fatemeh Salami, Soraya Balekianian

Department of Physical Education and Sports Science,

Education Management of Miandoab, Iran

Abstract:

The psychological disorders are common and serious problems that are found worldwide. The objective of present study is to compare the psychological health and job burnout of female athletic and non-athletic teachers of Miandoab Town. The present study is of causative-comparative type. The statistical population of present study includes the official female teachers of middle schools of Miandoab Town that amount to 182 individuals. The statistical sample is obtained through simple random sampling (based on Morgan table) which includes 120 individuals. The instruments of data collected used in the present study are Goldberg's General Health Questionnaire (1978) with reliability coefficient of 91 percent, and Maslach Burnout Inventory with reliability coefficient of 90 percent as defined in previous studies. To compare the elements, independent t-test is used. The findings show that there is a significant difference between psychological disorders and job burnout of female athletic and non-athletic teachers.

Keywords: psychological health, job burnout, athlete, non-athlete

1. Introduction

As shown in epidemiologic studies of psychological disorders in different countries, the prevalence of such disorders ranged between 10 to 40 percent (Yosefi and Yosefi, 2009). The risk of psychological disorders exists in each social stratum and within any union such

ⁱ Correspondence: email mostafa.mostafapour89@gmail.com

as the patients, engineers, or farmers (Shamlo, 2005). The respected profession of teaching is similarly susceptible to social and psychological pressures and damages. The teachers deal with minds and souls of the people, especially female teachers that educate the mothers and women of the next generation. In the past few years, the attention to job stresses has increases (Russell, 1987). Job burnout is one of the consequences of job stresses (Russel, 1987). Job burnout was first introduced in 1960s by Fridenberg. The most common definition of job burnout was introduced by Maslach and Jackson that defined it as a cognitive syndrome including emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal success. Emotional exhaustion refers to elimination of emotional sources.

Depersonalization refers to pessimistic tendencies and negative response to those who usually receive services from an individual. The reduction of personal success represents the reduction of feeling of competence in fulfilling personal duties and negative evaluation of oneself in regard to work (Soltanian and Bidokhti, 2010). Of proper and low-cost strategies with lack side effects for improving the psychological health and reduction of job burnout, one could point to athletic activities. The athletic competition might lead to improvement of psychological health, job satisfaction and increase of individuals' motivation (Schneider et.al, 2005). Based on the statistics of World Health Organization, about 43 percent of women do not exercise. The findings of a national study in Iran showed that more than 80 percent of population in Iran is physically non-active. In addition, 44 percent of Iranians do not exercise during their free time (Mazlomi et.al, 2011). The American Academy of Physical Education (1984) stated that physical activity is influential upon draining psychological stresses (Currie, 2004). Don et.al (2002) found out that one could use sport activities to treat weak to medium psychological disorders of adults in the age range of 25 to 45 years. Wilkinson et.al (2003) found out that doing athletic activities such as swimming and aerobic movements might be useful for athletics from psychological, physical and social dimensions. Honar Bakhsh et.al (2008) did a study on comparison of job burnout of female athletic and non-athletic teacher and reported that athletic teachers have more favorable conditions in regard to the three elements of job burnout compared with non-athletic ones.

2. Methodology

The present study is of causative-comparative type. The statistical population of present study included the official female teachers of middle schools of Miandoab Town that amounted to 182 individuals. The statistical sample was obtained through simple random sampling (based on Morgan table) which includes 120 individuals. The instruments of

data collected used in the present study are Goldberg's 28-item General Health Questionnaire (1978) with reliability coefficient of 91 percent and validity of 88-89 percent as reported in numerous past studies (Yaqubi and Palahang, 1996; Sadeqi and BaqirZade, 2009), 22-item Maslach Burnout Inventory with three subscales (emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and feeling of reduction of personal success) reliability and validity of which were respectively reported to be 80 and 90 percent as defined in previous studies (Sultanian and Bidokhti, 2010). To compare the elements, independent t-test is used.

3. Findings

Based on the following table, the level of psychological health of athletic teachers is more than non-athletic ones ($t=3.014$, $P<0.05$). In addition, the following table shows that there is a significant difference between athletic and non-athletic teachers in regard to the dimensions of job burnout. In other words, the athletic teachers feel emotional exhaustion ($t=2.30$, $P<0.05$), depersonalization ($t=-2.12$, $p<0.04$), reduction of personal success ($t=-1.87$, $p<0.001$) to less extent than their non-athletic colleagues.

Table 1: Comparison of Psychological Health and Job Burnout of Female Teachers

Variable	Groups	Number	Mean	SD	df	t	Sig
Psychological Health	Athletic	60	24.40	6.88	128	-3.014	-0.05
	Non-athletic	60	17.93	4.65			
Emotional Exhaustion	Athletic	60	10.31	10.17	128	-2.30	0.05
	Non-athletic	60	15.16	13.20			
Depersonalization	Athlete	60	3.12	4.079	128	-2.12	0.04
	Non-athletic	60	5.14	6.12			
Reduction of Personal Success	Athletic	60	12.15	10.19	128	-1.87	0.001
	Non-athletic	60	11.24	13.14			

4. Discussion and Conclusion

The findings of present study show that there is a significant difference between psychological disorders and job burnout of female athletic and non-athletic teachers so that the level of psychological health of athletic women is more than the non-athletic ones. The findings match the studies of Schneider et.al (2005), American Academy of Physical Education (1984, quoted by Currie, 2004), One et.al (2001), Currie (2004) and Wilkinson et.al (2003).

In addition, the results of present study show that the level of job burnout among athletic women is less than non-athletic ones. This matches the studies of Honar Bakhsh

et.al (2008), Schneider et.al (2005), and Wilkinson et.al (2003). Based on the findings of present study, one could state that doing athletic activities beside other treatment methods are influential upon psychological health and prevention and reduction of job burnout among female employees. Another significant issue is that exercise is among the least costly methods. Therefore, the development of public sports among employees and teachers along with provision of proper conditions and environment for them could contribute to psychological health, job satisfaction, and reduction of fatigue, depersonalization, and feeling of lack of personal success.

References

1. Honar Bakhsh, M. & Nejati, H. (2008). The comparison of job burnout of athletic and non-athletic teachers, Collection of Papers of Conference on Sport, Zanjan University
2. Mazlumi, S., S., Mohammadi, M. & Morovati, M., A. (2011). Exercise and its association with self-efficiency among employees of Yazd City, *Journal of Kerman University of Medical Sciences*, 7 (4), 346-354.
3. Palahang, H. & Yaqubi, N. (1996). Normalization of general health questionnaire, The Institute of Psychology, Tehran.
4. Sadeqi, M., R., Baqir Zade, R. & Haq Shenasi, M., R. (2009). The study of status of religious approach and psychological health of students of university of medical sciences of Mazindaran, University Research Council, Iran.
5. Shamloo, S. (2005). Psychological Health, Rosh Press, Tehran, 2.
6. Sultanian, M., A. & Amin Beidokhti, A., A. (2010). The study of the role of sport on job burnout of employee, *Scientific Journal of University of Medical Science*, 10, 4.
7. Yousefi, F. & Yousefi, M., H. (2009). The study of psychological health of high-school health of Sanandaj City, Collection of Papers of National Conference of Stress, Iran University of Medical Sciences, 345-346.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Authors will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflict of interests, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated on the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).